

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

MILESTONE REPORT

Workshop on industrial approaches for sustainable accelerators

(Cross Linking Accelerator R&D with Industrial Approaches)

MILESTONE: MS54

Document identifier:	IFAST-MS54
Due date of deliverable:	Month 42: October 2024
Report release date:	03/04/2024
Work package:	WP11: Sustainable concepts and technologies
Lead beneficiary:	GSI
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

The urgency of sustainable practices amid rising energy costs, with superconductivity emerging as a key technology was the core topic of the workshop. The discussions emphasized the need for long-term collaboration between accelerators and industries, navigating challenges posed by European procurement laws. The workshop on sustainability and energy efficiency in accelerators, focusing on superconducting systems as one of the most promising technologies in terms of their impact in future energy systems and energy efficiency of accelerator facilities. Technological perspectives such as the transition from normal conducting to superconducting systems, exploration of innovative cooling techniques, advancements in superconductor materials, and potential applications of paraffin wax impregnation have been discussed. Overall, the workshop aimed at fostering collaboration, addressing funding challenges, and bringing innovation in accelerator technologies to sustainable energy systems.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004730. IFAST began in May 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Approved by	Steering Committee		04/03/2024

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Executive summary

To identify challenges, needs, and opportunities for an enhanced and improved co-innovation between academic or public institutes and industry, a workshop was organized at GSI, Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany. The energy efficiency and sustainability-focused superconducting industry community was selected to participate in the relevant discussions.

"Superconductivity and Sustainability" served as the theme of a forward-looking workshop co-hosted by the GSI SIS100/SIS18 department, led by Dr. Peter Spiller, and the European superconducting industry association "CONNECTUS", chaired by Dr. Wolfgang Walter from Bilfinger Noell. The primary objective of the workshop was to enhance communication between the particle accelerator community and the superconducting industry while showcasing the latest developments in both fields. Representatives from numerous well-known European companies and public institutions participated in the event. Supported by GSI's technology transfer department, general aspects regarding how to improve efficiency in long-term, mutually beneficial high-technology collaborations between industry and public institutions were debated.

1 Introduction

There exists substantial potential for European research laboratories and industries to embrace innovative concepts, fostering heightened sustainability and energy efficiency in accelerators. This strategic approach not only promotes the technologies developed for advanced accelerator applications for use in energy systems but also aligns with the broader goal of promoting sustainable practices at both public and private facilities.

The imperative of sustainability takes center stage for major European accelerator laboratories such as GSI, FAIR, CERN and others, along with numerous counterparts across the continent. Recognizing the urgency, it becomes crucial to explore strategies for curbing the energy consumption of large-scale plants over the medium term. A tangible example involves the replacement of copper coils, notorious for energy losses through dissipation, with superconducting coils. Such a transition holds the promise of significantly reducing the energy consumption of beam guidance systems.

The workshop emphasized the paramount importance of strengthening collaboration between accelerator centers and industries in shaping the future landscape. A consensus emerged on the necessity for long-term collaboration and early industry involvement in the development of high-tech products. Recognizing the need for optimization, adjustments to legal framework conditions were deemed beneficial. The European AIPF forum has taken on the responsibility of addressing precisely these challenges, with the goal of documenting results as guidelines for the early and enduring engagement of industry in the progressive development of accelerator centers. This proactive approach reflects a commitment to creating an environment conducive to sustained collaboration, innovation, and the seamless integration of high-tech solutions into accelerator technologies.

Figure 1: Group photo of the workshop participants "sustainable energy systems and accelerator research and development"

2 General scope of the workshop

At the workshop[1], there was a lively exchange on the demand for further improvement of key parameters and performance. Presentations showcased studies and developments aimed at increasing the energy efficiency of large accelerator facilities and energy systems in the public sector. A central topic focused on synergies in the development of future superconducting technology with respect to its application in particle accelerators and energy systems. The I.FAST program ("Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology"), in which GSI/FAIR is involved in several work packages, served as the foundation and motivation for the workshop. GSI's contributions to the project include the development of new superconducting cables and approaches for the sustainability and energy efficiency of particle accelerator facilities.

European energy supply systems are undergoing significant transformation, which necessitates the development and implementation of new technologies. Superconductivity can play a pivotal role, particularly in terms of converting energy systems. At present, energy is predominantly transported in liquid, solid, or gaseous forms to supply a large portion of our society's energy needs, primarily via pipe systems and tanker trucks. A transition from chemical to electrical energy sources would require massive amounts of energy to be transported by cable (i.e., the existing electrical grid infrastructure) in the future. However, high line losses and constraints can be expected under these conditions, which could potentially be avoided using superconducting energy cables. Current developments at GSI/FAIR, CERN, and other future particle accelerator technologies are providing

substantial impetus in this regard and can contribute to societal benefits. Particularly notable advancements in the mass production of high-temperature superconductor materials and reductions in cost will enable large-scale applications in the future.

3 Challenges, Needs and Opportunities for Industrial/Academic Cooperation

3.1 GENERAL DRIVERS AND ISSUES FOR CO-INNOVATION

The rising energy costs pose a significant challenge for research organizations, impacting the operational duration of accelerator facilities. Facilities like CERN and GSI, major contributors to scientific research, grapple with high energy consumption. For instance, the Heavy Ion Therapy accelerator in Heidelberg consumes 25% of the clinic's energy, making Carbon ion beam treatments less attractive as energy prices escalate. Acknowledging this, science and technology review organizations, including the Helmholtz Association, recognize the imperative to reduce operation and energy costs. GSI has responded proactively by establishing a dedicated organizational unit, directly linked to its board of directors, focusing on this critical issue.

Superconductivity emerges as a promising technology to mitigate energy dissipation in accelerator facilities. Applications such as HTS energy-saving magnets, superconducting linear accelerators, and MgB₂ cables for power transmission hold significant potential. Leveraging superconductivity can lead to the development of concepts that not only lower energy consumption but also contribute to sustainable and cost-effective research in the future.

In the realm of high-tech industries, long-term collaborations and early industry involvement in research and development are pivotal. However, European procurement laws, designed to ensure fair competition, transparency, and equal opportunities, pose challenges. These laws, while essential for ethical practices, can hinder collaborations by requiring repeated qualification processes for multiple suppliers. Applying these laws to high technology, with its unique requirements for long-term partnerships, may inadvertently impede the development of innovative solutions and technologies.

Conferences and workshops like the Big Science Business Forum play a vital role in bridging the gap between procurement laws and the needs of high-tech R&D collaborations. These platforms facilitate communication, allowing stakeholders from academia and industry to discuss needs, challenges, and potential partnerships. Such initiatives can contribute to more effective collaborations in the future.

P. Spiller's introductory presentation at GSI highlighted various approaches in high-technology areas to increase energy efficiency campus-wide and for accelerator operation. Notable R&D focuses on energy-saving HTS Magnets, superconducting linear accelerators, power grid monitoring systems, sensor-based energy monitoring, Nuclotron cable development, FAIR energy consumption prediction, cooling system design, and high-current pulsed magnets for energy-efficient beam transport.

3.2 OPEN GROUP DISCUSSIONS

In session 6 of the workshop, “Open group discussion on challenges, technological perspectives and future opportunities for industry and academia” have been organized. In order to work out common answers, a set of three topics were discussed in mixed, industrial/academic groups at round tables.

3.2.1 Challenges in industrial/academic cooperation

3.2.1.1 Starting Points

- What goes well in terms of industry/academia cooperation? What are the barriers (e.g., legal aspects and framework conditions; mutual standards (quality & safety); ability to act / speed; resources; access; data sharing)?
- What can be improved?
- What fosters this cooperation?
- How to improve implementation and validation of technical innovations?
- Are there funding opportunities for sustainability that should be explored jointly?
- What role do communication formats such as joint workshops or large events like the BSBF play? Which are helpful in exploring opportunities for cooperation?
- What role do joint associations and communities of interest have here?
- How can these challenges and their suggested improvements be addressed to policy-makers?
- How can commercial interest and exchange of expertise be balanced?

3.2.1.2 Main Discussion Topics

The workshop identified a critical issue surrounding the inadequacy of funding opportunities, especially during the pivotal transition phase between proof-of-principle studies and the development of commercial prototypes. The consensus underscored the essential need for continuous funding spanning 2 to 4 years to facilitate the robust development and implementation of emerging technologies. Unfortunately, the current funding landscape falls short in providing the necessary resources for these crucial phases. The application process for funding grants is perceived as sluggish and cumbersome, impeding the pace of innovation. Furthermore, legal frameworks and regulations are viewed as impediments to long-term collaboration between research institutions and industries, with challenges arising in aligning interests and objectives in R&D collaborations and commercial procurement processes.

To address these challenges, it is imperative to identify successful models of collaboration between academia and industry that allow both parties to leverage each other's expertise and resources. Promising approaches include establishing joint research labs or centers, fostering partnerships for the exchange of knowledge and resources, and implementing open innovation strategies that aim to commercialize new technologies in the long term.

The development of new technologies inherently involves risks that stakeholders must acknowledge. Industries, at times, may exhibit reluctance to heavily invest in R&D due to associated financial risks, while the intricacies of managing intellectual property rights (IPR) can act as a deterrent for potential collaborative partners. Moreover, academia needs to broaden its scope to address social challenges by exploring solutions within industries, identifying synergies that may not be immediately apparent through independent research.

The workshop also emphasized the disparity in time scales between basic research in accelerators and commercial energy systems. While basic research projects often extend over a decade, commercial energy systems necessitate faster development cycles, typically within five years. Additionally, the limited technological overlap between basic research and commercial applications was highlighted, revealing challenges in collaboration and knowledge transfer. Despite sharing fundamental concepts, the divergent priorities of each sector can impede effective collaboration.

In summary, the workshop brought to light several challenges encompassing funding, collaboration, risk management, intellectual property rights, and time scales. Addressing these challenges through effective partnerships, open innovation strategies, and a broader scope of thinking is crucial for propelling innovation in accelerator technologies and contributing to the development of sustainable energy systems.

3.2.2 Technological perspectives and upcoming R&D needs/trends in sustainable energy systems and particle accelerators in industry and academia.

3.2.2.1 Starting Points

- How can different fields/markets profit from each other (material/resources/expertise)? Can we identify common interest clusters to bundle effort?
- What are critically needed improvements in performance and key parameters of superconducting systems (e.g., cooling, system design...)?
- How can a reduction of energy consumption and thus operating costs be achieved?
- Can we reduce our consumption and corresponding cost of consumables in superconducting systems (Helium, electricity)?
- In which new technical areas could superconductivity have added-value and may be applied in the future?
- What are tangible opportunities and synergies in the field of superconductivity, particle accelerators and energy efficiency between industry and RIs?

3.2.2.1 Main Discussion Topics

Innovative cooling techniques are being explored to improve efficiency and reduce cryogenic consumption in accelerator systems. Conduction Cooling, for instance, involves the natural transfer of heat through conduction to dissipate energy from various components. Another approach, Intelligent Cooling, employs advanced systems that adapt their operation based on real-time data and optimization algorithms, maximizing efficiency and minimizing energy consumption. Refrigerators are another option for cooling magnets, eliminating the need for gaseous helium (GHe) and providing an alternative solution for certain applications.

Increasing the operating temperature of superconducting components can reduce the cryogenic penalty; however, it's essential to consider that cryo-coolers are not highly efficient in large-scale applications. In such cases, refrigerators may be a more suitable choice. These innovative cooling techniques aim to optimize the performance and efficiency of superconducting components in accelerator systems.

J. Arnsberg's presentations focused on advancements in efficiently cooling current leads. The development of mixed refrigerant cycles and combined function current leads, incorporating both heat exchangers and conductors, emerged as key strategies to optimize efficiency in these critical components. These innovations hold great promise for enhancing the overall performance of superconducting systems.

Speakers A. Wulff, F. Gömöry, and T. Winkler addressed the challenges associated with AC losses in specific applications. Their talks highlighted ongoing efforts to develop large-scale production techniques for long lengths of superconducting tapes while minimizing AC losses. This research aims to make superconducting materials more practical and cost-effective for widespread use.

A notable area of research discussed at the workshop involves upgrading existing magnets using superconducting coils. This includes replacing traditional copper coils with superconducting ones or redesigning magnets to incorporate superconducting materials. These approaches seek to improve the performance and efficiency of existing accelerator infrastructure, showcasing a pathway for sustainable upgrades in the field.

Several presentations emphasized the potential role of artificial intelligence in optimizing cooling systems and accelerator operations. AI algorithms can analyze real-time data from accelerators, enabling the prediction and prevention of potential issues while maximizing overall efficiency. The integration of AI technologies stands out as a promising avenue for advancing the capabilities of superconducting systems.

The workshop provided a platform to explore potential synergies between accelerator research and mainstream industrial high-temperature superconducting (HTS) technologies. Recognizing the mutual benefits of collaboration, participants discussed how advancements in one field could positively impact the other, fostering interdisciplinary approaches to sustainable energy solutions.

An alternative cooling method for superconducting magnets discussed at the workshop is the use of paraffin wax impregnation. This technique, requiring less training compared to epoxy-based methods, has the potential to save liquid helium (LHe) and reduce the overall environmental impact. The exploration of such alternative cooling methods aligns with the broader goal of making superconductivity more accessible and environmentally friendly.

Overall, these innovative cooling techniques aim to improve efficiency, reduce cryogenic consumption, and optimize the performance of superconducting components in accelerator systems.

3.2.3 Future concepts and future applications.

3.2.3.1 Starting Points

Questions for discussion

- Do you have ideas how to apply superconducting technologies in fields of energy efficiency?
- Which improvements or modifications of sc cables would empower new commercial applications, especially applications in energy systems?
- Is there infrastructure that could be made available to each other? (e.g., cryogenic test stands/plants, labs, ...)

- In which areas does industry strive to carry out developments jointly with public institutions.
- Development goals for HTS magnets – where do we go?
- Future cooling concepts for HTS applications?
- Many applications are on the horizon. What are thresholds and key milestones?

3.2.3.2 Main Discussion Topics

Discussions on financial topics of the workshop underscored the challenges faced by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in financing innovation. The high costs associated with innovation, especially when a clear business case is lacking, often hinder the progress of SMEs. The imperative for more accessible funding options and robust support systems for SMEs became apparent, emphasizing the critical role that financial structures play in fostering a culture of innovation and growth within smaller businesses. Moreover, the discussion on magnetocaloric cooling introduced a novel concept for efficiently cooling large-scale infrastructures like transmission grids. By exploring the use of gas coolant cooled with magnetocaloric means at intermediate stations, the workshop hinted at potential breakthroughs that could revolutionize cooling methods for expansive systems.

Talks about the open labs concept shed light on the challenges small labs face in accommodating external projects due to existing workloads and limited capacities. In contrast, larger labs are better equipped to handle additional collaborations. The talks by L. Rossi and U. Gambardella on the IRIS project provided valuable insights into the distributed infrastructure for superconductivity. With a focus on power transmission and magnet applications, IRIS has laid the groundwork using MgB₂ cables developed by ASG. As funding is expected to continue until at least 2025, this initiative has the potential to become a significant resource for various applications beyond its initial focus, offering a glimpse into the future of collaborative infrastructure projects.

Further discussions looked on balancing industry interests and partnerships highlighted the pragmatic approach industries must adopt for upcoming particle accelerator projects. Ensuring profitability while effectively managing risks is paramount. Concepts such as stage-wise contracting and EU innovation partnerships emerged as suitable frameworks for collaborations between industries and research institutions. By leveraging each other's expertise and resources, both parties can navigate the challenges associated with large-scale projects. The industry's keen interest in applying spin-offs from accelerator research in energy products signifies a forward-looking approach. Collaborative efforts in common development projects for energy systems and technology transfer concepts, including licensing agreements, present exciting opportunities to drive innovation and sustainability in the energy sector. These initiatives represent a bridge between cutting-edge research in particle accelerators and real-world applications that can shape the future of energy technology.

4 Workshop Summary

The workshop proceedings highlighted the significant potential for European research laboratories and industries to adopt innovative approaches, enhancing sustainability and energy efficiency in accelerators. This strategic focus positions accelerators for advanced applications in energy systems, aligning with broader efforts to promote sustainability in both public and private facilities.

Major European accelerator laboratories, including GSI and FAIR, recognize the urgency of addressing sustainability challenges. Strategies to curb energy consumption in large-scale plants were discussed, with a notable example being the transition from copper coils to superconducting coils to reduce energy losses in beam guidance systems.

The workshop underscored the paramount importance of strengthening collaboration between accelerator centers and industries. A consensus emerged on the need for long-term collaboration and early industry involvement in developing high-tech products. Efforts to optimize collaboration, including adjustments to legal framework conditions, were discussed, with the European AIPF forum taking a proactive role in addressing these challenges and documenting guidelines for industry engagement.

In the broader scope of the workshop, discussions covered the demand for improvement in key parameters and performance, focusing on increasing energy efficiency in large accelerator facilities and energy systems. The I.FAST program provided the foundation, with GSI's involvement in developing superconducting cables and sustainability approaches for particle accelerator facilities. The transformation in European energy supply systems and the potential of superconductivity in converting energy systems were also highlighted.

Challenges, needs, and opportunities for industrial/academic cooperation were addressed, including the impact of rising energy costs on accelerator facilities. Superconductivity emerged as a promising technology to mitigate energy dissipation, with applications such as HTS magnets, superconducting linear accelerators, and MgB₂ cables. Collaboration challenges, especially in the context of European procurement laws, were discussed, emphasizing the role of conferences and workshops in bridging gaps.

Open group discussions delved into challenges, technological perspectives, and future opportunities for industry and academia. Funding challenges during the transition phase between proof-of-principle studies and commercial prototypes were identified. Successful models of collaboration, the importance of addressing social challenges, and the disparity in time scales between basic research and commercial energy systems were emphasized.

Technological perspectives and upcoming R&D needs in sustainable energy systems and particle accelerators were explored. Innovative cooling techniques, advancements in high-temperature superconductor materials, and the potential of paraffin wax impregnation for cooling superconducting magnets were discussed.

Finally, discussions on future concepts and applications covered financial challenges faced by small and medium enterprises, the concept of magnetocaloric cooling for large-scale infrastructures, challenges in accommodating external projects in open labs, and the pragmatic approach industries must adopt for upcoming particle accelerator projects. The potential for collaborative infrastructure projects, such as the IRIS project, highlighted the evolving landscape of accelerator technologies and their broader applications.

5 References

- [1] “Superconductivity for Sustainable Energy Systems and Particle Accelerators,” GSI Indico (Indico). Accessed: Jan. 10, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://indico.gsi.de/event/17548/>